

MEDICINE IN THE AGE OF THE SHAYBANIANS

Mahmud Hasani

Doctor of history

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Abstract. *This article will explore people's knowledge in medicine and treating. It can explore some feature of alternative medicine that can be described.*

Keywords: *Shaybani, manuscript, anus, Dastur ul-ilaj, Muqaddimah, science of medicine.*

During the Shaibani dynasty, founded by Muhammad Shaibani Khan (reign years 1500-1510), the science of medicine was also given importance. One of the works that was written during this period and became famous later is the work "Dastur ul-ilaj" ("Program for treatment"). The author of "Dastur ul-ilaj" Sultan Ali Khurasani (15th-16th works) wrote this work in 933/152-1527 and it is dedicated to Abu Mansur Kochkinjikhhan (1510-1530) from the Shaibani. 7 manuscript copies of this work are kept in the Fund of the Federal Republic of Uzbekistan with item numbers 2264/2, 757/3, 11261/1, 3653/3, 11634/4, 11297, 7269/2. The oldest copy of the work is kept under number 2264/2. The manuscript was copied in 1589 and consists of 261 pages. There is a seal on the last sheet, which says Abdulaziz ibn Nasruddin Khoja al-Husaini, 1212. The next oldest one is number 757/3 and belongs to the 16th century. Copied by Bekmuhammad ibn Sayyid Muhammad. It consists of 190 pages, the last two pages are missing.

The number 11261/1 of the work is complete and was copied in 1728 by the order of Khudoibanda Bahadur Ghazi ibn Abdurashid Khan, nicknamed Erka Khan[1]. This copy was kept in the hands of Basitkhan ibn Zahidkhan Shoshi, a famous scientist, poet and physician from Tashkent. The remaining copies belong to the 19th century.

In the introduction to his work, Sultan Ali writes that he has been engaged in medicine and treatment in Khurasan, Movarounnahr, in particular, Samarkand, for 40 years[2]. According to him, all the khans and nobles in the palace in Samarkand turned to him for healing. In particular, Abul Muzaffar Mahmudshah Sultan, who was from the Shaybanites, called him to Akhsi and treated him. After recovery, he offers Sultan Ali to write a book about medicine and treatment. "Even though I have very little time," he writes, "this treatise was written in accordance with His Majesty's instruction and was named Dastur ul-Ilaj"[2].

The work consists of two articles, the first article is about diseases specific to a particular organ and their treatment. The article, in turn, consists of 25 chapters, each chapter is divided into several chapters, and the chapters are divided into varieties.

The second article is about diseases that do not belong to a specific member and is divided into 8 chapters, each chapter is divided into several chapters, and the chapters are divided into varieties (parts).

The contents of the articles and chapters are as follows:

The first chapter of the first article deals with diseases of the head and consists of 17 chapters. The second chapter is about eye diseases and contains 26 chapters. The third chapter deals with diseases of the ears and consists of six chapters. The fourth chapter deals with diseases of the nose and it consists of seven chapters. The fifth chapter deals with diseases of the lips and consists of four chapters. The sixth chapter is about dental diseases and it covers several chapters. The seventh chapter is about gum and periodontal diseases, it consists of three types. The eighth

chapter is about diseases of the mouth and tongue, consisting of ten chapters. The ninth chapter deals with the diseases of the throat and small tongue, and contains seven chapters. The tenth chapter is about the lungs, lung tract, chest diseases, and consists of seven chapters. The eleventh chapter is about the heart, its ailments and cures, and consists of four chapters. The twelfth chapter is about diseases of the esophagus, consisting of four chapters. The thirteenth chapter is about stomach ailments, consisting of 21 chapters. The fourteenth chapter is about liver diseases, symptoms and treatment, divided into seven chapters. The fifteenth chapter is about the evils of divorce, consisting of four chapters. The sixteenth chapter deals with the causes, symptoms and treatment of diseases of the liver and spleen, consisting of two chapters. The seventeenth chapter deals with diseases of the bowels, consisting of eight chapters. Eighteenth chapter contains several chapters on diseases occurring in the anus, its causes, its causes, symptoms and cures. The nineteenth chapter deals with diseases of the kidneys, in several chapters. The twentieth chapter is about bladder disorders, which includes several chapters. Chapter twenty-one consists of 18 chapters on penile and ovarian disorders. The twenty-second chapter is about uterine diseases, causes, symptoms and cures, consisting of 16 chapters. The twenty-third chapter deals with diseases of the breast, covering several chapters. The twenty-fourth chapter deals with diseases of the membranes in the chest, consisting of two chapters. The twenty-fifth chapter contains several chapters on scoliosis, back pain, gout, scurvy, varicose veins, and "Elephant disease".

The second article deals with specific non-organ diseases and consists of eight chapters. The first chapter is about fevers, their types, causes and symptoms, and their treatment, and consists of several chapters. The second chapter is about swellings and rashes on the surface of the skin and covers several seasons. The third chapter is about diseases of the skin and other organs, their causes and symptoms, treatments, and consists of seventeen chapters. The fourth chapter is about "snake disease" and "fox disease" and other diseases, consisting of several chapters. The fifth chapter is about injuries, without a season. The sixth chapter deals with wounds, of two kinds. The seventh chapter is about knocking, falling, breaking, exits, several varieties. The eighth chapter is about poisons, consisting of three chapters.

The above-mentioned manuscript numbered 2264/1-2 is noteworthy, not only in terms of its antiquity, but also in terms of structure. Although headings in the text of the gold-water table appear separately in red ink, these headings are also outlined in red ink in large letters. This helps to easily find the chapters and chapters in the book. The most important thing is that the names of diseases and plants are outlined in black ink and a glossary is given. It is known that in medical works written in Persian and Turkish languages, the names of diseases and plants are usually left in Arabic, which makes it difficult for a reader who does not know Arabic to use the work. This difficulty is solved in the manuscript, even the framework of this work can be called an Arabic-Persian dictionary.

It is written on the first page of "Dastur ul-ilaj" that these dictionaries written on the edge of the book, checking and comparing them were the work of Akhund Mulla Abdulgafur and Qazi Arabshah. At the top of this page, Abdulaziz Bahadur Khan's seal is stamped. The second medical work written during the Shaibani period was written by Sultan Ali Tabib Khurasani and was called "Muqaddimai Dastur ul-ilaj" ("Preface to Dastur ul-ilaj"). 6 copies of this manuscript are stored in the fund of the Academy of Sciences of Republic Uzbekistan Oriental Institute under item numbers 757/1, 2264/1, 3663/2, 10925/6, 7269/1 11124.

This is an addition to the author's earlier work "Dastur ul-ilaj". About its writing, the author says: After the book "Dastur ul-Ilaj" is written, some saints, if something is written about the theoretical part of medicine and the vein, bohran (crisis) and other signs, this book (i.e. "Dastur ul-Ilaj") will be perfect. and a monument would have remained on the page of life, they said. For this reason, the "Preface" of this book was written[2].

The author writes here that he presented this book to Sultan Abu Sa'id Bahadur Khan (1530-1533) and says that he has been in his service for twenty years. This "Preface" is placed at the beginning of the manuscript number 2264 mentioned above and copied in 1589. "Introduction" consists of 16 chapters and covers general issues of medicine, such as health care, vein, urine, crisis, air.

The first chapter of the "Introduction" is called "On Health" and consists of 16 chapters. The second chapter is about the limits, scientific and practical benefits, pillars, mizaj, types of repentance and consists of 19 chapters. The third chapter is about knowing the structure of normal organs and this chapter is divided into seven chapters. The fourth chapter is about knowing the structure of complex organs and it consists of 19 chapters. The fifth chapter is about powers and it consists of 5 chapters. The sixth chapter is about knowing the diseases that occur from external influence, collaboration, client, simple and complex organs, consists of 6 chapters. The seventh chapter is about veins, it consists of 20 chapters.

The eighth chapter is about the benefits of breathing. The ninth chapter is about obtaining evidence from urine, which consists of 20 chapters. The tenth chapter is about determining a person's disease based on food waste, which includes 7 chapters. The eleventh chapter is about determining the disease according to the sweat, it is divided into five chapters, the twelfth chapter is about the condition of the blood, it consists of five chapters. The thirteenth chapter has its own chapter on determining illness based on the state of the body. The fourteenth chapter is about birth and death and contains 6 seasons. The fifteenth chapter deals with signs and symptoms of recovery, non-recovery, hope and despair, divided into 11 chapters. Sixteenth chapter crisis. The eleventh chapter is about the crisis. Consists of 8 seasons.

"Dastur ul-Ilaj" together with "Muqaddimah" were printed in Lahore, India in 1878, 1880, 1890 and 1899 by lithographic method. The volume consists of 334 pages. At the end of the book, the publishers write about this work: "It is an extremely useful work on the science of medicine for both young and old, and its benefits are incalculable."¹ The publishers also noted that they prepared this copy by comparing several manuscripts.

It should be mentioned that "Dasutr ul-Ilaj" and its "Preface" are written in simple and fluent language, the division into chapters, seasons and parts makes them easy to use. Sentences and meanings are stated succinctly and clearly without too much detail. The fact that it has been published several times is proof of our word.

In conclusion, the science of medicine, along with other sciences, had its development during the Shaibani period. The above-mentioned "Dastur ul-Ilaj" and its "Preface" had an impact on the development of medicine of the next period.

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